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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 824077

CRUISE REPORT

iMAR 2022: Integrated assessment of the distribution of
Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems along the Mid-Atlantic
Ridge in the Azores region – Cruise Report

RV Pelagia, Cruise No. 64PE506, Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise
28/07/22 - 04/08/22, Horta (Portugal) - Horta (Portugal)

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1 Summary

The iMAR_2022 cruise “Integrated assessment of the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR) in the Azores region” took place aboard the Research Vessel Pelagia of the Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ) between July 28th and August 4th 2022. This expedition was the second leg of the iMAR cruise funded by the SEA OCEANS program of Eurofleets+ and the H2020 European project iAtlantic. It was led by the University of the Azores (Portugal) in collaboration with the Hydrographic Institute (IH), the University of Porto (Portugal), the University of Aarhus (Denmark), the National Oceanography Center (United Kingdom), GEOMAR (Germany), the University Museum of Bergen (Norway), the PP Shirshov Institute of Oceanology (Russia), and the University of Vale do Itajaí (Brazil). During this cruise we explored under-visited portions of the southern sector of the MAR in the Azores region and associated ridges and seamounts between 300 and 1,200 m depth (Figure 1): (1) unnamed seamount (coded B14) and Alfa seamount, (2) ridges around the Menez Gwen hydrothermal vent area, (3) A16 seamount and Cabeçote hills, (4) Sarda N and Sarda NE seamounts, (5) Farpas ridge, and (6) Voador seamount. On most sampling locations we collected multibeam data, CTD measurements, water and sediment samples, as well as towed camera video transects along with ADCP data to survey deep-sea coral and sponge communities. Water samples will be used to characterize water masses properties (nutrients and physical-chemical parameters) and also for biodiversity analyses through eDNA methods. Sediment samples (collected at 1,000 m depth) will be used for biodiversity analyses through faunal studies and eDNA methods, presence of microplastics, granulometry analyses, and physical-chemical studies.

Although the data has yet to be analysed in detail, the iMAR 2022 cruise revealed some interesting discoveries. We have identified new areas that fit the FAO definition of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VME), and compiled valuable scientific information to inform the development of policies that promote the preservation of the natural heritage, ensuring the sustainable use of the deep sea, minimizing negative impacts on these vulnerable ecosystems. The video transects that aim to characterize the benthic communities revealed an impressive aggregation of the octocoral *Hemicorallium triocolor* on the crest of an unexplored ridge, together with bamboo corals, stylasterids and large fan-shaped sponges. In the eastern ridge of Menez Gwen we also discovered that very high bottom current speeds, as suggested by the movement of the whip corals, may be one of the factors for the observed low diversity and abundance of corals and sponges in some areas. On the Farpas ridge we discovered a massive garden, covering hundreds of meters, of the primnoid coral *Narella* spp. With the highest densities ever observed in the Azores so far. Artificial intelligence algorithms might be necessary to get all those corals annotated.

The multibeam bathymetric surveys revealed that several locations in the southern part of the MAR are shallower than previously mapped. For example, the Best West was found to be much shallower and with more structures than previous maps indicated. The new bathymetry revealed a 4 km long

summit shallower than 1,000 m depth, adding a new area to our list of exploration targets. Such areas may not have been fished before and are fundamental for understanding what ecosystems looked like before they were impacted by fishing activities, hence being considered as reference sites and priority areas for conservation. These new discoveries will contribute with scientific information to the development of policies that promote the preservation of the natural heritage, ensuring the sustainable use of the deep sea, minimizing the negative impacts on these very vulnerable ecosystems. The expedition contributed significantly to the Instituto Hidrográfico program (Mapping the Portuguese Sea) and to the international initiative and the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

Cruise statistics: 7 days at sea, 1,030 km of transits, 10 areas visited, 4,030 km² of seabed mapped (mainly in the south portion of the MAR inside the EEZ of the Azores), 12 dives with the NIOZ video system that resulted in 33 hours of deep-sea images over 29 km of seabed, 7 stations for the analysis of water mass properties and to collect sediments, which resulted in 87 (water) plus 102 (sediment) samples for environmental DNA, 31 samples for the analysis of water nutrients, 30 (water) plus 6 (sediments) for microplastics, 6 samples for bacteria, and 6 samples for meiofauna.

Figure 1 - Working area and track chart of RV Pelagia (Cruise 64PE847 / iMAR). Bathymetry from Okeanos-UAz and EMODnet.

2 Research Programme/Objectives

The Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR) is the most prominent ocean seafloor feature in the Atlantic Ocean, dividing it into eastern and western deep basins. The unique setting of the Azores, at the triple junction of the European, American and African plates and in close proximity to the ridge, offers an exceptional opportunity to survey the role of the MAR in shaping the distribution of deep-sea megabenthic communities, mostly those considered Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs). The diverse geomorphology and complex oceanography patterns surrounding the Azores have generated an extraordinary diversity of benthic communities, making the area a hotspot for cold-water corals in the North Atlantic. Latitudinal gradients and dissimilarities between the deep-water coral fauna on both sides of the MAR were noted at local and wider scale studies, raising the question on whether the MAR can represent a boundary for the biological dispersion between the eastern and western Atlantic. However, there has been considerably few explorations on seamounts, ridges and other topographic features along the MAR.

The iMAR_2022 cruise “Integrated assessment of the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR) in the Azores region” took place aboard the Research Vessel *Pelagia* of the Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ) between July 28th and August 4th 2022. This expedition was the second leg of the iMAR cruise funded by the SEA OCEANS program of Eurofleets+ and the H2020 European project iAtlantic. The iMAR cruise aimed to evaluate the role of the MAR in shaping latitudinal and trans-Atlantic patterns in deep-sea biogeography, connectivity and spatial distribution of deep-sea megafauna. Additionally, the cruise aimed to (i) map and characterize deep-sea coral and sponge communities inhabiting unexplored seamounts and ridges along the MAR in the Azores region; (ii) identify new areas that fit the FAO’s VME definition; (iii) add to the existing knowledge on the environmental drivers that determine the spatial distribution of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the MAR and finally (iv) determine the condition of benthic communities by looking at evidence of fishing damage to fauna and the presence of lost fishing gear and marine litter.

The original iMAR cruise was proposed to last 18 days and visit 11 different areas along the MAR. Survey sites were selected along a latitudinal gradient of the MAR within the Portuguese EEZ around the Azores, between 42° and 36° N. We suggested the exploration of some under-visited portions of the MAR and associated ridges and seamounts between 300 and 1,500 m depth. Tentative areas to explore included from N to S: (1) South Chaucher, (2) unnamed seamount coded as D12, (3) the Kurchatov fracture zone area, including Isolado and D10 seamounts and ridges complex, (4) unnamed seamount West of Oscar seamount coded as D5, (5) the Gigante seamount and ridges complex, (6) Cavala seamount, (7) uncharted area SW of Flores island, and (8) Menez Gwen ridges, (9) unnamed seamount coded as A3, (10) the Cavalo ridges, and (11) Farpas ridge.

On each sampling area, we aimed to collect multibeam data for seabed mapping, together with towed camera transects to identify deep-sea benthic communities, water samples for biodiversity analyses through eDNA methods, and sediment samples for biodiversity analyses through faunal studies and eDNA methods, microplastics and analyses of granulometry and physical-chemical studies. Water mass properties were also characterized by sampling seawater and measuring physical-chemical parameters.

The research plan included a sampling methodology that combined (1) the collection of detailed multibeam and backscatter data for seabed mapping, (2) the analysis of water mass properties using CTD data, seawater samples collected with Niskin bottles in a Rosette, and measurements of physical-chemical parameters, (3) the collection of seawater samples for biodiversity analyses through eDNA, (4) the collection of sediment samples with a box-corer for biodiversity analyses through faunal studies and eDNA methods, the presence of microplastics and analyses of granulometry, physical-chemical studies, and bacterial growth, and (5) the recording of high-definition video images of the seabed using the towed camera system of RV Pelagia, accompanied by ADCP data, to identify and characterize deep-sea benthic communities.

The results of this work contribute to the aims of the MapGES and the H2020 iAtlantic projects to understand the factors that control the distribution, stability and vulnerability of deep-sea ecosystems and better inform sustainable management throughout the Atlantic in an era of unprecedented global change. The iMAR cruise also aimed to enhance the predictive capabilities for VMEs, and to inform Good Environmental Status (GES), Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and provide new insights on how to sustainably manage deep-sea ecosystems in the MAR. Finally, this cruise contributes to the SEAMAP 2030 (Mapping the Portuguese Sea) program of the Portuguese Hydrographic Institute and to the international Seabed 2030 initiative and the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

3 Narrative of the Cruise

July 28th 2022 – Loading and departure from Horta

We were lucky to have two research vessels exploring the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR) at the same time. While following the NOAA Okeanos Explorer as part of the Voyage to the Ridge campaign, we started the second leg of our Eurofleets+ cruise iMAR - Integrated assessment of the distribution of VMEs along the MAR in the Azores. We left the IMAR and Okeanos University of the Azores building in the morning, packed with all the necessary material and equipment for the cruise (Figure 2). Without COVID-19 on the way, we were able to have 11 scientists on board as part of the crew. We started loading the *RV Pelagia* at around 10:30 and stayed on-board for the rest of the day. After lunch, the team participated in the familiarization event that included the safety procedures of the vessel and organized the two containers allocated for the cruise (acclimatized seawater and sediment labs) and the video room where video operations are monitored (Figure 3). We left the Horta harbour at 16:30 and stopped for a short multibeam calibration operation in the middle of the Faial-Pico channel. We started the transit to B14 and Alfa seamounts with the multibeam (MB) system on (st001), stopping after dinner for a quick Sound Velocity Profile (st002) when water depths reached 1,200 m. At around 19:40, we resumed the transit and the multibeam survey (still st001) on the way to B14, adding a couple of MB survey lines on B14 before the next station.

Figure 2 – Loading the NIOZ RV Pelagia for the Eurofleets+ & iAtlantic iMAR cruise.

Figure 3 – The iMAR 2022 cruise planning meetings started right after leaving the harbour.

July 29th 2022 – Unnamed seamount coded B14 and Alfa seamount

First day of work of the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise on the MAR south of the Azores. We managed to fulfil today's schedule, with successful sampling with the video system, CTD, multibeam, VMADCP, and TV-guided box-corer (Figure 4). We started the day at the unnamed seamount coded B14 with a video survey with the NIOZ towed-camera system (st003), starting at 08:50 (Figure 5). After fixing some last-minute issues and adjusting our GoPro cameras, we descended to 1,100m depth and started the transect with the vessel mounted ADCP recording. After lunch, we had a safety drill to practice the abandon ship procedure and performed a Rosette/CTD cast (st004; 13:55) at about 930 m and a TV-guided box corer (st005; 15:20) at around 1,000 m depth. Both instruments worked perfectly and we got enough water in the Niskin bottles and sediments on deck from the box-corer for the sampling activities. All water (pH, nutrients, and eDNA) and sediment (fauna, eDNA, microplastics, and bacteria) samples were successfully collected and processed, although the reduced amount (approx. 15 cm) of sediment in the corer prevented to obtain all desired slices for eDNA. We then transited to the Alfa seamount, about 30 nm west of B14, where we performed a shorter towed-camera video transect (st007; 17:40) between 980 and 650 m depth, with the ADCP turned on (Figure 5). The NIOZ engineers managed to fix the positioning system of the video frame, which started pinging during the last 30 minutes of the dive. Both the water filtration and the sediment eDNA sampling prolonged until after dinner. Meanwhile, we started the MB survey (st008) in the Alfa seamount to finish the coverage of this area. We then transited to the Menez Gwen, where we had the time to do a couple of MB lines. We had a debriefing meeting at around 21:00 and discussed the communication plan for the cruise.

Figure 4 – First day of work of the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise, on the MAR south of the Azores. We managed to fulfil today's schedule, with successful sampling with the video system, CTD, multibeam, VMADCP, and TV-guided box-corer.

Figure 5 - Track of the towed-camera video transects st003 and st007 on the unnamed seamount coded B14 and Alfa seamount.

July 30th 2022 – Menez Gwen

There have been multiple research expeditions to Menez Gwen, but most of them targeted the hydrothermal vents, with only a few of them exploring the adjacent ridges and mounds. Today we were able to perform 2 video transects, one CTD cast, one box-corer and multiple MB lines (Figure 6). After looking at the multibeam data collected in the southern portion of the Menez Gwen area, we selected the locations for the towed-camera video surveys (st009; 08:00). The first video transect was performed on the eastern ridge with a south-north direction (Figure 7). The dive explored 2,850 linear m over the seabed, covering depths between 710 and 1,000 m. After 4 hours at the seafloor, the video frame got entangled on a thick rope, preventing the structure from continuing moving forward. The dive had to be aborted to bring the structure back to deck. Due to the entanglement in a thick polypropylene line, damage was detected at the end of the umbilical of the video frame, and the engineers decided to fix it before it got worse. Meanwhile, we conducted a CTD/Rosette cast (st010; 13:30) down to 810 m depth on a small mound between the two main ridges of Menez Gwen. Besides the regular water samples, today we also sampled at 700 m depth for pH measurements and filtered 60 L of water for microplastic analyses from 5 and 700m depth. We then conducted a blind box-corer (st011; 15:20) that revealed to be unsuccessful, before managing to get a corer full of sediment (st012; 16:40) to carry out all the analyses. With the exception of the water filtration for microplastics, the sampling finished before dinner. Since no video transects could be done in the afternoon, we decided

to head towards an uncharted seamount north of Menez Gwen (-31.283W; 38.315N) to verify its geomorphology and minimum depth (st013-st015). We had a scientific crew meeting at 20:30 to make a summary of the day and plan the next. We continued the MB survey until the next morning.

Figure 6 – Today, during the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise, we explored the eastern ridge of the Menez Gwen.

Figure 7 - Track of the video transect (st009) in Menez Gwen.

July 31st 2022 – Unnamed ridge coded as A16 and Cabeçote

The multibeam surveys completed during the night on the seamount west of Beta showed that the area was much shallower and with more structures than previous maps showed (Figure 8). It revealed a 4 km long summit shallower than 800 m, adding a new area to our list of exploration targets. The MB surveys finished on the location of the first station of the day, coded as A16. The Portuguese Hydrographic Institute (IH) mapped this large area southeast of Flores island back in 2019. The MB data revealed a large ridge-like structure similar to Sarda seamount, with extensive areas at 1,000 m depth and its shallowest point at about 650 m. Today, we explored two of the ridges mapped in 2019, one with no name (coded as A16) and the other one named Cabeçote (Figure 9). We started the day with a 4.8 km long video transect (st016; 08:40) on A16, covering a depth gradient between 1,200 m and 740 m depth (Figure 10). During the transect, the video frame hit a hard rock, damaging one of our camera housings and breaking the camera inside. We lost one of our GoPro cameras, one battery and one microSD memory card. During the video survey, we selected a location for the CTD deployment (st017; 13:55) at around 1,000 m depth, in an area with only sparse megafauna of the genus *Acanella* and *Chrysogorgia*. All water measurements and samples were collected, including 40 L of water filtered for microplastic analyses. There was a bit of delay on this and the next stations. We then moved to a flat at 1,000 m depth area to deploy the TV-guided box-corer (st018; 15:40). The box-corer successfully closed at the seafloor but was brought to deck with a reduced amount of sediment. We collected all samples for marine litter, fauna and bacterial studies, but only the first 4 slices of the cores for eDNA analyses. During this deployment we agreed that next time, after detecting the seabed on the video images, the corer should be brought higher on the water column before dropping it on the seafloor. We then started an 11 nm transit to the next station on Cabeçote ridge. Here, camera 2 of the video frame stopped working when the system got in the water, and the frame had to be brought back to deck for repair. After about one hour of work, the technicians managed to detect the problem in the connection cable. We started the video transect (st019) at around 19:15 and finished it a bit later than usual, at about 21:30 (Figure 10). We had a scientific crew meeting in the evening to review the daily operations and plan the next day. The last operation of the day was a MB survey (st020)

passing over two areas with low quality bathymetry, finishing on the first station of the next day.

Figure 8 – Bathymetry of the Beta West before (left) and after the night surveys (right) of the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise. The area was much shallower and with more structures than the previous maps showed.

Figure 9 – Today, we explored two of the ridges mapped in 2019, one with no name (coded as A16) and the other named Cabeçote. Top left is the NIOZ video frame, top right is the Rosette / CTD, middle left is the box-corer, and middle right is the multibeam room, bottom left is updating the cruise logs, and bottom right is the Captain during the video transect.

Figure 10 - Track of the towed-camera video transects st016 and st019 in the unnamed ridge (coded as A16) and Cabeçote

August 1st 2022 –Unnamed ridge baptised as Sardinha (little Sarda, meaning sardine) and NE Sarda

During the night, we mapped over the Cabeçote SE and A10 geomorphologic structures to increase the details already contained on our maps. Previous surveys on this area were compiled in a bathymetry map named MAR90. There were no massive changes or additions to the pre-existing maps. Today, we changed the order of the planned activities to optimize the vessels' operations. After arriving to the unnamed ridge baptised as Sardinha (little Sarda, meaning sardine), we conducted a “blind” Rosette/CTD (st021; 08:25) cast at 977 m depth, before the video survey (Figure 11). As usual, we measured pH and sampled different Niskin bottles for nutrients, eDNA and extra microplastic analyses. At around 09:30, we started the first video transect (st022) of the day on the top of the Sardinha ridge, from 1,050 to 650 m depth (Figure 12). The video frame was brought on deck before lunch with one of our camera housings partly flooded. We lost another one of our GoPro cameras, one battery and one microSD memory card. We moved to the next station about 10 nm SW of the last video position. During the transit, we started a new MB survey (st023; 12:24) and passed over a structure shallower than 1,000 m to verify its morphology. At Sarda NE, we did a blind box-corer (st024; 15:10) on a flat area and collected enough sediment for all samples. In fact, this was the first time that we collected sediment for all eDNA samples. The faunal sieving produced 4 bottles of material for posterior laboratory analyses. We then moved to the next video station on a major ridge-like structure on Sarda East area. This dive (st025; 16:30) covered about 3.2 km of the seafloor between 840 and 575 m depth (Figure 12). The hopper video frame was brought to deck at 20:00 and we started transiting to the East side of the MAR with the MB pinging and recording (st026; 20:10). We had a scientific crew meeting at 20:45 and planned the stations for the next day.

Figure 11 – Today, we explored an unnamed ridge baptised as Sardinha (little Sarda, meaning sardine) and NE Sarda. The photos portrait part of the daily life on board RV Pelagia, including our media team in action.

Figure 12 - Track of the video transects st022 and st025 in the unnamed ridge (coded as A16) and Cabeçote

August 2nd 2022 – Farpas ridge

During the night, we transited from the west of the Ridge axis on the American tectonic plate to the Euro-Asian plate on the east. After arriving to the Farpas area, we continued the MB surveys that helped producing better resolution maps to plan the location of the different stations for the day. We selected a location for the CTD/Rosette cast (st027; 08:00) at 955m depth that the video revealed to be an area with the octocoral *Candidella imbricata* and the black coral *Leiopathes cf. expansa*. All samples planned were completed (Figure 13). We then moved to the first waypoint of the video transect (st028; 09:15) and covered about 3.8 km of seafloor between 1170 to 650 m depth (Figure 14). The vessel-mounted ADCP was not turned on during this station. We then conducted a blind box-corer on a flat area close to the main ridge of Farpas. It was a successful corer, full of sediment for all the sampling to be done. We were able to collect 6 samples for eDNA, 3 for microplastic analyses, 1 for bacteria and 1 for faunistic characterization. When then transited to the next station, where we finalized the multibeam survey (st030; 14:20) to cover a gap left during the survey of the night before. The second video transect of the day (st031; 15:20; Figure 14) was interrupted when the top camera of captured a bunch of lost fishing lines that seemed to get entangled on the video frame. The captain of RV Pelagia reversed the vessel following the same track and, fortunately, got the frame free. For precaution, the video frame was brought to the surface and checked for damages, to then be prepared for the next deployment. We decided to cancel the remaining surveys for the day. During the evening we had the usual lab meeting and relaxed a bit playing some games. The MB surveys towards Voador seamount (st032) started at 19:00 and lasted until the next morning.

Figure 13 – We sampled the Farpas ridge area after crossing from the west of the Ridge axis on the America tectonic plate to the Euro-Asian plate on the east.

Figure 14 - Tracks of the video transect st028 and st031 in the Farpas ridge

August 3rd 2022 – Voador ridge

During the transit from Farpas to Voador, we obtained bathymetry data with better resolution than we previously had, adding extra details to several areas, including Voador de Baixo (Voador South). As in previous days, we started the day with a blind CTD station (st033; 08:10) in an area that the video revealed to have very little benthic megafauna. Everything went as planned and we collected all the necessary samples, including extra water for microplastic analyses (Figure 15). We placed the vessel at the beginning of a small ridge in Voador de Baixo, where we performed the first video transect of the day (st034; 09:21; Figure 16). The new multibeam data came in time to help with the navigation of the video frame over the top of the ridge, which covered depths between 1230 and 830 m depth. Because we had to leave the last station of the day at around 19:00, we decided to make the second video transect right after lunch. This transect (st035; 13:30) was conducted from north to south on a ridge located in the eastern side of the seamount, starting at 670 m and reaching 545 m, almost at the shallowest part (Figure 16). After almost 2 hours of transecting over soft sediment or bare rock with almost no visible fauna, we decided to bring the video frame on deck, reposition the vessel, and conduct a new video survey on the opposite side of the seamount structure. This short dive (st.036; 16:00; Figure 16) lasted only 40 minutes over the seabed and covered a very narrow depth range (685-700), but unveiled a dense aggregation of primnoids, which got the scientific crew excited after the low diversity observed previously. After the video transect, we performed a box-corer (st037; 17:20) that was brought to deck with very little sediment and was mostly composed of coral rubble. There was enough sediment for the bacteria, fauna and microplastic samples, but only allowed for 2 cores and 5 samples of sediments for eDNA. In any case, this was a promising sample for faunistic studies. We started transiting back to Faial with the MB on (st038; 18:20) and passed over specific waypoints to optimize filling some gaps on the bathymetry data along the eastern ridges of the MAR.

Figure 15 – Images of the last day of the Eurofleets+ & iAtlantic iMAR 2022 cruise, when we explored the Voador seamount area.

Figure 16 - Tracks of the video transects st034-st036 in Voador seamount.

August 4th 2022 – Arriving in Horta; end of cruise

We arrived back to Horta harbour at around 08:30 in the morning. The morning was dedicated to pack all samples and gear, copy all files and clean the cabins. We left RV Pelagia at around 13:30 local time. During the afternoon, we unpacked everything at the premises of the University of the Azores.

4 Preliminary Results

Multibeam surveys

During the iMAR 2022 cruise, we performed 11 stations for MB surveys, summing 94:35 hours, with 4,030 km² of mapped seabed. The areas mapped were mostly seamounts/ridges on the southern section of the MAR in the Azores EEZ, in deeper areas during many of the 1,030 km of transits (Figure 17). The MB bathymetric surveys covered some new ground and help complete some areas that were previously mapped (Figure 18). For example, the surveys conducted on an unexplored seamount west of Beta (st015) showed that the area is much shallower and with more structures than previous maps showed. It revealed a 4 km long summit shallower than 800 m and added a new area to our list of exploration targets. On the other hand, we mapped the Cabeçote SE and A10 geomorphologic structures (st020) to increase the details already contained on previous maps, but with no significant changes or additions to the pre-existing information. We also obtained bathymetry data on Voador de Baixo (st038), with better resolution than we previously had, adding extra details to many areas. The main results of the MB surveys are presented as maps of the data collected after undergoing a preliminary cleaning and post-processing treatment.

Figure 17 – MB surveys conducted during the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise on the southern sector of the MAR inside the Azores EEZ.

Figure 18 – Details of the MB surveys conducted during the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise.

CTD and Water samples

During the iMAR 2022 cruise we performed 7 stations for the analysis of water mass properties, which resulted in 93 pH measurements, 31 samples for nutrient analyses and 87 samples for environmental DNA (eDNA) (Figure 19). These stations were complemented with 2 stations for generating sound velocity profiles (SVP).

Water eDNA samples

Similarly to the iMAR 2021 cruise, seawater from a variety of depths was collected from a total of 7 sampling areas using a CTD-rosette equipped with 24 x 10 L sampling bottles. Where possible, water samples for eDNA analysis were collected from a pre-defined location identified during the previous video transect. Following the retrieval of the CTD, triplicate seawater samples (~4L) were filtered

through 0.2 µm Sterivex™ filters using a peristaltic pump in a 10°C temperature-controlled laboratory. The eDNA on the filter was immediately preserved using RNAlater preservative and then stored at -80°C. Once the filter units are transported to the UK, eDNA in the samples will be analyzed in a dedicated clean lab using both DNA metabarcoding (multiple markers) and for targeted single species detection using quantitative PCR (qPCR) with species-specific primers. The specific qPCR assays conducted will be largely informed using information from the towed video transects and based on species of interest and importance. For the metabarcoding approach, eDNA will be extracted from all samples and gene fragments will be amplified and sequenced (paired end) using an Illumina MiSeq system. Four DNA markers from four gene regions (cytochrome c oxidase I, 18S rRNA, 12S rRNA, and 16S rRNA) will be used to assess biodiversity in these samples. The raw sequence reads will be demultiplexed, quality filtered and then clustered into operational taxonomic units (OTUs). The OTUs will be denoised and taxonomically assigned to the best possible taxonomic resolution using several sequence databases.

The results from both multiple marker and single marker analysis will be used to assess biodiversity at the sample areas. As the deepest water samples were taken as close to the seabed as possible, these samples will provide valuable information about both pelagic and benthic communities in the form of presence/absence data which will be compared to the data extracted from the video images. Between sampling areas, the number of OTUs detected and the number of unique OTUs for each metabarcoding marker will be compared to give an indication of the composition of the deep-sea community at each sampling area.

Figure 19 – Location of the stations for the analysis of water mass properties and sound velocity profiles (SVP) conducted during the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise.

Box corer

During the iMAR cruise we performed 6 successful box-corer stations and collected 100 samples for environmental DNA, 18 for microplastic analyses, 6 samples for bacteriological studies, and 6 samples for meiofauna analyses (Figure 20).

Sediment eDNA

Following the transport of the frozen sediment samples on dry ice to the laboratory, DNA will be extracted from a subsample of each sediment sample (~20g) from all sampled layers. Short DNA fragments will be amplified using several metabarcoding primers. The exact metabarcoding markers have to be finalized, but it is expected that they will likely include the cytochrome c oxidase I (COI) subunit gene and potentially a hypervariable region of both 18S and 16S genes. Following the construction of Illumina amplicon libraries and sequencing, a metabarcoding pipeline for prokaryotes and eukaryotes will be applied. The metabarcoding results will be presented as OTUs or amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). The results will be used towards a deep-sea biodiversity assessment of the marine eukaryotic and prokaryotic communities in the sediment between 0 and 30 cm depth from each sampling area. Close attention will be paid to any identical/matching OTUs also present in the water eDNA datasets depending on the proximity of the exact sampling area.

Bacterial analyses

To better understand the metabolically diverse microorganisms found in deep-sea sediments sampled along the MAR in the Azores region, we will attempt to grow and isolate marine bacteria colonies present in sediment corers using marine-agar culture plates in the laboratory. Bacterial colonies will contribute to the growing marine bacterial collection at IMAR, while bacterial physiological activities are envisaged to address the question of bacterial adaptation to fluctuating environmental conditions and activities. Collected bacteria might reveal interesting enzymes with biotechnological applications, such as the discovery of antibacterial activity against known pathogen and new protease activities of interest for biomass transformation, e.g., lignocellulosic activity. In addition, we will also investigate the ability of deep-sea marine bacteria to synthesize structurally diverse classes of bioactive secondary metabolites with high biotechnological potential.

Figure 20 – Location of the box-corer sampling stations conducted during the Eurofleets+ iMAR 2022 cruise.

Shipboard (S-) ADCP

Similarly to the IMAR 2021 cruise, shipboard (S-) ADCP data were collected during the video transects. On-station and underway current velocities and relative acoustic backscatter data were collected with a 75-kHz Teledyne RD Instrument (RDI) Ocean Surveyor system mounted in the ship's hull along with ancillary data of ship position, pitch and roll and heading. The software RDI VmDAS was used to configure instrument setup, data communication (ship position, ship heading) and data acquisition. The vertical bin size was set to 8 m (first bin at 16 m) and the total sampling range was 100 bins (800 m). The transducer offset relative to the ship's keel was set to 45°. Repeated ADCP surveys were largely conducted on-station at different video stations.

Single ping ADCP data will be post-processed using the Common Oceanographic Data Access System (CODAS) from the University of Hawaii following the GO-SHIP guidelines for shipboard ADCP measurements. The main CODAS processing steps will include time-averaging of single ping data into 120 second ensembles, water track calibration to estimate any remaining transducer offset and calculating absolute current velocities by removing the ship velocity from the ADCP ensemble velocities. The final dataset will include the following variables: Time, depth (m), u-velocity (m/s), v-velocity (m/s), acoustic backscatter (echo amplitude in raw counts).

Video surveys: Deep-sea benthic communities

Both the iMAR 2021 and 2022 cruises aimed to evaluate the role of the MAR in shaping latitudinal and trans-Atlantic patterns of deep-sea biogeography and connectivity, and the spatial distribution of deep-sea benthic megafauna. To achieve this goal, we mapped and characterize deep-sea coral and sponge communities inhabiting unexplored seamounts and ridges in the Azores Region; identified new areas that fit the FAO's VME definition; and added valuable information to the existing knowledge on the environmental drivers that determine the spatial distribution of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the MAR. Finally, these cruises contributed with data to determine the condition of benthic communities by looking at evidence of fishing damage to fauna, presence of lost fishing gear and marine litter. All these objectives were achieved with a detailed sampling programme with the towed video system developed by NIOZ. During the iMAR 2022 cruise, we conducted 12 dives that resulted in 33 hours of deep-sea images over 29 km of seabed (Figure 21). The following sections will provide a succinct summary of the main observations made at each video station.

Figure 21- Location of the Hopper video dives conducted during the Eurofleets+ iMAR cruise.

St. 003 – St. 007. Unnamed seamount coded B14 and Alfa seamount

We started the video exploration with the NIOZ video frame at the unnamed seamount coded B14 (st003; 08:50). The frame reached the seabed at 9:20 and left the bottom at 12:30, covering approximately 3.1 km of seabed. The first dive (1100-520 m depth) came with surprises, with an impressive aggregation of the octocoral *Hemicorallium triocolor* on the crest of this unexplored ridge, together with bamboo corals, stylasterids and large fan-shaped sponges (Figure 22). We also drifted over some deep-sea fish species including orange roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*), monkfish (*Lophius*

piscatorius), and kite fin shark (*Dalatias licha*). Unfortunately, the positioning system of the video frame was not working properly.

At Alfa seamount, we performed a shorter video transect (st007; 17:40) at depths between 980 and 650 m, with the ACDP turned on. The deepest areas of the dive contained some aggregations of the octocoral *Hemicorallium triocolor* together with stylasterids, some occasional fan-shaped sponges, and several other sponge species of the genus *Pheronema*, *Asconema*, *Regadrella*, *Phakelia* and *Geodia*. Towards shallower areas, where slopes were steeper, we drifted over communities of extensive gardens of *Narella verslyusi*, *Leptopsamia formosa*, and several sponge species (e.g., *Haliclona magna*) (Figure 22).

Figure 22 – The first dives with the video frame came with surprise, with an impressive aggregation of the octocoral *Hemicorallium triocolor* on the crest of an unexplored ridge, together with bamboo corals, stylasterids, and large *Haliclona magna* and fan-shaped sponges.

St. 009. Menez Gwen

The video transect (st009; 08:00) in the Menez Gwen area was performed on the eastern ridge following a south to north direction. The dive explored 2,850 linear meters of seabed, covering a depth gradient between 710 and 1000 m. Most of the dive occurred over unconsolidated sediments: sands, gravels, coral rubble and boulders of varying sizes. The diversity of species observed along the dive was predominantly low, increasing towards the shallowest areas of the ridge (Figure 23). In the deepest part, a few sparse black corals of the genus *Leiopathes*, sea urchins of the species *Cidaris cidaris* and small *Lophelia* colonies were observed, always in the form of isolated organisms. Below 780 m depth, some areas hosted aggregations of the primnoid *Narella verslyusi*, always in low abundances, and accompanied by some other coral species such as *Hemicorallium triocolor* and *Paramuricea* sp. The

movement of the whip corals on the shallowest part of the ridge denoted high bottom current speeds, which in some instances turned the video frame sideways.

Figure 23 –The diversity of species observed along the E ridge of Menez Gwen was predominantly low, increasing towards shallower areas. The observed movement of the whip corals of the genus *Narella* denoted the presence of high bottom current speeds.

St. 016 – St. 019. Unnamed ridge coded as A16 and Cabeçote

The first video transect (st016; 08:40) was performed on A16 ridge, and covered 4.8 km of seafloor in a depth gradient between 1200 m and 740 m depth. The dive started in an area of large basaltic boulders and rocks, with sparse colonies of black and bamboo corals attached to the hard substrates, including large colonies of the genus *Leiopathes* (Figure 24). Some fan-shaped sponges (likely *Phakellia*) were also observed. The sandy patches in between the rocky outcrops hosted less species, including the ubiquitous bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* attached to either soft and hard substrates, and also the foraminifera cf. *Syringamina fragilissima*. Just below 1000 m depth, aggregations of stylasterid corals started to appear, in some areas reaching high densities, and stretching to depths of 800 m. The community then shifted to a dominance of desmosponges (most of a small size) for a few meters along the slope. At around 615 m depth, dense aggregations of large octocorals, likely from the genus *Placogorgia*, were observed. These aggregations appeared in two spots, both on the upper part of the slope and on the top of the ridge. A few meters below, at 680-700 m depth, dense aggregations of primnoids of the genus *Narella* were reported, generally associated to the gorgonians *Acanthogorgia* sp. and *Callogorgia verticillata*.

At the Cabeçote ridge, we conducted one video transect (st019) between 19:15 and 21:30, covering 1,400 m of seafloor. The dive started at 1000 m depth in an area of coral rubble with a few sparse rocks that were colonized by the corals *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia* sp., as well as several species of

glass sponges, such as *Farrea occa* (Figure 24). The area did not hold much epibenthic life until reaching depths of 800 m, where an aggregation of the glass sponge *Asconema* sp. and the octocoral *Acanthogorgia* sp. was observed, together with a variety of other species in varying densities, such as the small white coral *Pleurocorallium johnsoni* and the large fan-shaped sponge *Phakellia* sp. Once at the top of the ridge, at 700 m depth, the community changed to a coral garden dominated by octocorals of the genus *Narella*, together with *Acanthogorgia* sp. Interestingly, this coral garden shifted to one dominated by the small octocoral *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, in some areas reaching impressive densities. Before the end of the dive, an aggregation of stylasterids was also observed, changing again to a coral garden of *Narella* until the end of the dive.

Figure 24 - Images of the benthic communities and species observed on two of the ridges explored, one coded as A16 and the other one named Cabeçote. We started the day with a 4.8 km long video transect on A16, covering a depth gradient between 1200 m and 740 m depth and finished with a shorter transect on Cabeçote.

St. 022 – St. 025. Unnamed ridge baptised as Sardinha (little Sarda, meaning sardine) and NE Sarda

We conducted one video transect (st022) on the top of the Sardinha ridge, from 1050 to 650 m depth. The dive started in an area of high slopes covered in large quantities of coral rubble, where some glass sponges were attached to. Some orange roughy passed by gently swimming in front of the camera. When vertical walls were encountered, some black corals of the genus *Leiopathes* were reported, together with the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula*. In some areas, aggregations of stylasterids were observed, in some instances reaching high densities, indicating that some of the coral rubble could be originated by this species. The dive moved relatively fast up the slope through areas of little fauna, including the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* and some glass sponges of the genus *Asconema*. The shallowest part of the dive, between 670 and 640 m depth, hosted large numbers of the giant sponge *Characella pachastrelloides*.

We conducted one video transect on a major ridge-like structure on the Sarda East area. This dive (st025; 16:30) covered about 3.2 km of seafloor between 840 and 575 m depth. The video frame landed in a very abrupt area, with large rocky outcrops colonized by stylasterids and several species of sponges, some attaining large sizes. While going up the slope, the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* appeared alongside the stylasterids, together with large fan-shaped sponges of the genus *Phakellia*. Some areas hosted relatively high densities of *Pheronema carpenteri*, which shared the habitat with primnoids of the genus *Narella* below 800 m depth. This community dominated the area explored for most of the dive, with a change in the dominance towards the shallowest part (~600 m), where the yellow octocoral of the genus *Acanthogorgia* became the most relevant invertebrate species.

Figure 25 – Images of the benthic communities and species observed on the unnamed ridge baptised as Sardinha (little Sarda, meaning sardine) and NE Sarda.

St. 028 – St. 031. Farpas ridge

The first video transect (st028; 09:15) covered about 3.8 km of seafloor from 1170 to 650 m depth. The dive (Figure 26) started on an area of a complex geomorphology, with large rocks colonized by plexauridae corals not yet identified to species level and large fan-shaped sponges of the genus cf. *Phakellia*. The rocks rapidly shifted to sedimentary areas characterized by the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* and the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*. Once the video frame started to move up the slope, the first colonies of the white octocoral *Candidella imbricata* started to appear, increasing in density towards 1,000 m depth, with several dense aggregations observed along the path until depths of around 940 m. Once the video frame reached 800 m depth, the community shifted to coral gardens dominated by the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *Narella bellissima* and the sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*. The density of the primnoids of the genus *Narella* increased to reach some of the highest densities ever observed in the Azores, lasting for hundreds of meters. Some of the associated species of this dense gardens were the octocoral *Acanthogorgia* sp. and the fan shaped sponge *Phakellia* sp. The shallowest part of the dive was characterized by the octocorals *Acanthogorgia* sp. and *Callogorgia verticillata*.

The second video transect of the day (st031; 15:20) covered a large depth range, between 1250 and 650 m depth (Figure 26). The video frame landed in an area of soft sediments with several eel-like fishes swimming very close to the seabed. Once we reached the slope and started moving up, sponges of the species *Pheronema carpenteri* started to appear, being relatively ubiquitous during the deepest part of the dive. Once the hard substrates appeared, the community shifted to that characterized by the octocoral *Candidella imbricata*, in some areas reaching high densities, especially on the basaltic rocks. The shallowest areas had gorgonian corals of the genus *Acanthogorgia*, although no further exploration could be done due to an entanglement on a fishing line.

Figure 26 - Images of the benthic communities and species observed on the Farpas area, including the large aggregations of primnoids of the genus *Narella*, bird's nest sponges *Pheronema carpenteri*, large fan-shaped sponges of the genus cf. *Phakellia* and several species of octocorals.

St. 034 – St. 035. Voador ridge

The first video transect of the day was performed in a small ridge of Voador de Baixo seamount (st034; 09:21). It started on an area of soft sediments with *Lebensspuren* clearly visible over the sand, but with little epifauna observed. Once the video frame started to move upslope, aggregations of coral rubble

started to appear, which were colonized by several glass sponges (e.g., *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Asconema* sp.). Some hard substrates had small yellow corals likely from the species *Leptopsammia formosa*. It is interesting to report that at 900 m depth, a patch of what it seemed to be the hydrocoral *Pliobothrus symmetricus* was observed. While moving up the slope, aggregations of the bird's nest *Pheronema carpenteri* became more common, in some cases covering distances of several tens of meters. High densities appeared at around 850-750 m depth, usually accompanied by corals of the genus *Narella*.

A second video transect (st035; 13:30) was conducted from north to south on a ridge located in the eastern side of the seamount, starting at 670 m and reaching 545 m depth, almost at the summit. Surprisingly, this transect hosted very little fauna all along, with no aggregations of any large species to be reported. The most commonly observed fish was the bluemouth rockfish (*Helicolenus dactylopterus*), which appeared scattered along most of the dive. A third transect was conducted on the opposite side of the seamount structure. This short dive (st.036; 16:00) lasted only 40 minutes over the seabed, and covered a very narrow depth range (685-700). We landed over a dense aggregation of the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *Narella bellissima*. The aggregation lasted some tens of meter until it shifted to a sponge ground of the glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*. This species dominated most of the area, although not reaching densities as high as those observed in previous dives. In between the patches with *Pheronema carpenteri*, some areas hosted relatively high numbers of the pedunculate sponge *Stylocordilla pellita*, which had been observed mostly as solitary individuals in the previous two dives in the same geomorphological structure.

Figure 27 – Examples of the benthic communities observed in Voador ridge, including aggregations of the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* and primnoids of the genus *Narella*.

5 Data and Sample Storage / Availability

This cruise collected and generated four main types of data: multibeam bathymetry data, CTD and ADCP data, water and sediment samples, and video images of the seafloor. Multibeam bathymetry data is being used to characterize the geomorphology of the seamounts and ridges surveyed during the cruise and to produce GIS layers of bathymetry. CTD and water samples are being used to characterize the water mass properties of the different areas along the MAR. Towed camera video data is being used to characterize and map the benthic communities inhabiting different portions of the MAR, some of which can be considered VMEs. Water and sediment samples will be used for eDNA analyses contributing to the understanding of the distribution of the biodiversity along the MAR. Sediment samples will also be used for the quantification of micro-plastics. Since the iMAR cruise is embedded in the H2020 iAtlantic project which, in turn, is participating in the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORD), we will strictly follow iAtlantic and ORD Data Management Standards and comply with FAIR data approach to make the data produced Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

All datasets produced during the cruise will be made openly available under creative commons licenses. However, in order to give enough time for data analyses and the preparation of publications derived from the study of deep-sea benthic habitats along the MAR, an embargo of a maximum of two years will be requested. This complies with timelines set by the iAtlantic Data Policy.

As defined in the Eurofleets+ Data Management guidelines for cruise and programme applicants and grantees, the raw data and metadata produced during the cruise will be provided within the following timelines:

- Metadata of the cruise (SeaDataNet Cruise Summary Report): within two weeks after the Cruise
- Metadata of the datasets of the cruise: within two months after the cruise
- en-route data: via EARS, automatically
- CTD data and data of deployed devices: within two months after the results are obtained
- "manual" data, e.g. observations and/or measurements on samples: within two months after the results are obtained to allow for lab analyses

6 Participants

No.	Name	Early career	Gender	Affiliation	On-board tasks
1	Telmo Morato	N	M	UAZ	iMAR cruise PI. Overall coordination of operations
2	Marina Carreiro-Silva	N	F	UAZ	iMAR cruise co-PI. Coordination of the CTD/water sampling work
3	Carlos Dominguez-Carrió	N	M	UAZ	Coordination of the towed camera system operations. Co-PI of the cruise
4	Luís Rodrigues	N	M	UAZ	Processing of multibeam bathymetry data and derivatives
5	Tenente José Murta	Y	M	IH	Coordination of the Multibeam surveys
6	Teresa Cerqueira	Y	F	UAZ	
7	Manuela Ramos	Y	F	UAZ	Identification of deep-sea benthic fauna from video images
8	Guilherme Gonçalves	Y	M	UAZ	Identification of deep-sea benthic fauna from video images
9	Inês Carneiro	Y	F	UAZ	Coordination of the box-corer sampling work
10	João Pereira	Y	M	UAZ	Video analyses for marine litter and fisheries impacts
11	Catarina Fazenda	Y	F	UAZ	Science communication
Remote Participants					
12	Susan Evans	Y	F	NOC	Coordination of the CTD/water sampling work
13	Christian Mohn	N	M	AAU	Physical oceanography of the North Atlantic
14	Timm Schoening	N	M	GEOMAR	Development of semi-automated methods for video analyses
15	Tina Molodtsova	N	F	P.P. Shirshov	Identification of deep-sea corals species from video images
16	Joana Xavier	N	F	UP	Identification of deep-sea sponge species from video images
17	J. Angel Perez	N	M	UNIVALI	Benthic community ecology expert
18	Christopher K. Pham	N	M	UAZ	Video analyses for marine litter and fisheries impacts
19	Julie Robidart	N	F	NOC	Molecular ecologist
20	Manuel A. Malaquias	N	M	UIB	Identification of deep-sea sediment infauna

UAZ: University Azores, Portugal; IH: Portuguese Hydrographic Institute; NOC: National Oceanography Centre, UK; AAU: Aarhus University; GEOMAR: GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research, Germany; P.P. Shirshov: P.P. Shirshov Institute of Oceanology, Russian; UP: University of Porto, Portugal; UNIVALI: University of Vale do Itajaí, Brazil; UIB: University Museum of Bergen, Norway.

7 Station List

Station No.	Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	WaterDepth	Gear	Remarks/Recovery
	2022	[UTC]	[°N]	[°W]	[m]		
1	28/07/2022	17:20	38.5073	-28.6213		Multibeam	Transit
2	28/07/2022	19:18	38.4188	-28.9658	500	SVP	Faial S
3	29/07/2022	08:50	37.7727	-30.6412	1100	Hopper	B14
4	29/07/2022	13:55	37.7695	-30.6470	932	CTD	B14
5	29/07/2022	15:22	37.7571	-30.6492	996	Boxcorer	B14
6	29/07/2022	16:11	37.7566	-30.6587		Multibeam	Transit
7	29/07/2022	17:28	37.7315	-30.8600	980	Hopper	Alfa
8	29/07/2022	20:15	37.7471	-30.8545		Multibeam	Transit
9	30/07/2022	08:08	37.8062	-31.5277	1000	Hopper	Menez Gwen
10	30/07/2022	13:30	37.8443	-31.5200	810	CTD	Menez Gwen
11	30/07/2022	15:21	37.8427	-31.4898	1006	Boxcorer	Menez Gwen
12	30/07/2022	16:40	37.8475	-31.4852	1060	Boxcorer	Menez Gwen
13	30/07/2022	18:07	37.8319	-31.4422	1500	Multibeam	Menez Gwen
14	30/07/2022	18:55	37.9278	-31.4078	700	SVP	Transit
15	30/07/2022	19:30	37.9278	-31.4078		Multibeam	Beta W
16	31/07/2022	08:41	38.1582	-31.9701	1214	Hopper	A16
17	31/07/2022	13:55	38.1653	-31.9698	976	CTD	A16
18	31/07/2022	15:42	38.1785	-32.0252	995	Boxcorer	A16
19	31/07/2022	19:14	38.0935	-32.2312	1018	Hopper	Cabeçote
20	31/07/2022	21:34	38.0645	-32.2190	1638	Multibeam	Transit
21	01/08/2022	08:25	37.7110	-32.6620	1016	CTD	Sardinha
22	01/08/2022	09:34	37.7140	-32.6608	977	Hopper	Sardinha
23	01/08/2022	12:24	37.6929	-32.6748	680	Multibeam	Transit
24	01/08/2022	15:12	37.4454	-32.8091	1000	Boxcorer	Sarda NE
25	01/08/2022	16:28	37.4602	-32.8307	875	Hopper	Sarda NE
26	01/08/2022	20:10	37.4244	-32.8462	670	Multibeam	Transit
27	02/08/2022	08:04	36.9462	-32.1645	970	CTD	Farpas S
28	02/08/2022	09:15	36.9533	-32.1598	1170	Hopper	Farpas S

Station No.	Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	WaterDepth	Gear	Remarks/Recovery
	2022	[UTC]	[°N]	[°W]	[m]		
29	02/08/2022	13:22	36.9551	-32.1221	998	Boxcorer	Farpas N
30	02/08/2022	14:18	36.9553	-32.1230	1322	Multibeam	Farpas N
31	02/08/2022	15:20	36.9927	-32.0522	1220	Hopper	Farpas N
32	02/08/2022	18:57	36.9727	-32.0621	577	Multibeam	Farpas N
33	03/08/2022	08:08	37.3872	-30.9742	1020	CTD	Voador
34	03/08/2022	09:21	37.3650	-30.9768	1200	Hopper	Voador
35	03/08/2022	13:33	37.4124	-30.9413	673	Hopper	Voador
36	03/08/2022	16:03	37.4238	-30.9523	706	Hopper	Voador
37	03/08/2022	17:27	37.4298	-30.9636	997	Boxcorer	Voador
38	03/08/2022	18:18	37.4345	-30.9392	694	Multibeam	Transit

8 Acknowledgements

This research cruise contributes to the overarching scientific mission statement of the Azores Deep-Sea Research group at Institute of Marine Sciences - Okeanos of the University of the Azores: *deepen our understanding on the natural diversity, ecosystem structure, function, connectivity and resilience of deep-sea communities in the Azores EEZ in a changing planet, while informing for a sustainable use of natural resources for current and future generations*. RV Pelagia ship-time was provided free of charge for the iMAR survey, as part of a project which received funding from the European Union's H2020 Research & Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 824077 (EUROFLEETS+). We would like to thank the Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ) for making the RV Pelagia available to Eurofleets+ and to our team in particular. The Azores Deep-Sea Research group is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 (H2020) programme under grant agreement No 678760 (ATLAS), No 689518 (MERCES) and No 818123 (iAtlantic), by the Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) under the pluriennial strategic project (UIDB/05634/2020) granted to Okeanos, the Program Stimulus of Scientific Employment (CCCIND/03345/2020 and CCCIND/03346/2020), the FCT-IP Project UIDP/05634/2020 and the PhD grant (PD/BD/111953/2015), by the Azores Government and PO2020 Açores under the MapGES (Acores-01-0145-FEDER-000056) and DeepWalls (ACORES-01-0145-FEDER-000124) projects as well as the PhD grant (M3.1.a/F/052/2015). We would like to thank the captain and crew of the RV Pelagia for their committed work during the whole iMAR cruise.